

Quantum Interference Due to Interaction with a Potential?

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Interference is very important in quantum mechanics, but it is apparently difficult to trace its physical origins. In early years of the subject, it appeared there were physical waves present interfering like classical waves, but no such waves were found experimentally. When writing a wavefunction $W(x)$ as a Fourier series, the various $\sin(px)$ (for a give symmetry) interfere, i.e. add or subtract depending on the point x . The form of the $\sin(px)$ wave already exists for a quantum particle in a box with no potential. In addition, the term $-\text{del}^2 W(x)$, which is found in the Schrodinger equation and in expressions for kinetic energy density, involves interference of various $\sin(px)$ terms in calculating kinetic energy. This is peculiar because a particle in a box has one kinetic energy $p^2/2m$ everywhere even though its wavefunction is $\sin(px)$. It seems it would be good to attempt to determine the origins of interference if possible. In this note, it is suggested interference is due to the interaction of a particle with a potential $V(x)$. It is argued that $W(x)$, the wavefunction, is a kind of average of a cycling scattering process with $V(x)$. $W(x)$ contains dynamic information that density $W(x)W(x)$ does not, but is nevertheless a somewhat static looking average as well. It is argued that a quantum particle is continually scattering in the potential in such a manner that a resonance occurs. Thus, $\sin(px)$ terms in $W(x)$ are "created" through this scattering, described by the term $V(x)W(x)$ in the Schrodinger equation. Given that a quantum particle may have zitterbewegung, i.e. forward and backward motion as it moves along with an average v , it seems that this zitterbewegung internal motion affects the scattering with $V(x)$ and may be the origin of interference. The interference which occurs when using average expressions such as the wavefunction $W(x)$, it is argued, is a consequence of this.

Quantum Particle in a Box

It is interesting to consider a quantum particle in a box which has $E=p^2/2m$ and a wavefunction $W(x) = C \sin(px)$. ($\sin(px)$ consists of "interference of a forward and backward moving wave $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$, but each of these contain $\sin(px)$, so $\sin(px)$ seems to be an internal part of a quantum particle.) The energy of the particle is apparently $p^2/2m$ for each x which is strange because the quantum particle has a density of $C^2 \sin(px)^2$ meaning it does not have a high probability to be very near the walls etc. If one, however, considers a 2x2 matrix model (1) or zitterbewegung model as describing the quantum particle, then the particle is undergoing a kind of forward and backward motion as it moves with an average velocity v in the forward direction. Thus, one might say that on average it has a kinetic energy of $p^2/2m$ everywhere, (as a kind of center of mass motion), but has an internal cycling motion which only allows it to have a probability distribution within a length of about a radius. This distribution could describe why the particle does not reach the wall. It is not a point, but rather has size. A second important feature to notice about $\sin(px)$ is that it can become negative. For the particle in the box, this does not seem to be a major issue as density is given by $W(x)W(x)$ and is the same whether $\sin(px)$ is positive or negative. Density is the physical observable so one does not have

to worry about such negative values. For a particle in a potential, however, things are very different. $W(x) = \sum_p f_p \sin(px)$ so at a given x one $\sin(px)$ may contribute a positive value, and another a negative.

Interference in a Potential

For a quantum particle in a potential, interference is important both in $W(x)$ and in calculations of average kinetic energy, as well as in calculations of various other averages. In both cases, it seems difficult to understand why one $\sin(px)$ term should partially cancel another at a point x . For the particle in a box, the kinetic energy is $p^2/2m$, so one would naively think that if such a particle were continuously scattered in a potential one would have a set of $f_p p^2/2m$ with no weights. For a quantum particle in a potential, the overall kinetic energy seems to be $\sum_p p^2/2m f_p^2$, but interference occurs in:

$$[\sum_p p^2/2m f_p \sin(px)]/W(x) + V(x) = E$$

with the first term being the average kinetic energy at a point. This average is taken over a long time, namely the cycle time $1/E$. Interference is critical in evaluating this average kinetic energy. The more physical kinetic energy density $1/2m W(x) \sum_p p^2/2m f_p \sin(px)$ also relies on interference of $\sin(px)$ terms. It seems difficult to describe why this interference occurs.

In classical physics, a particle is continuously interacting with a potential as it moves along x . At each x , this interaction is described by $-dV(x)/dx$ and one knows x , t and $v(x)$ at each point. In quantum mechanics, one cannot describe the particle with x, t and $v(x)$ at each point, because it has the possibility, due to zitterbewegung, of being in a region of the length of a wavelength. Nevertheless, scattering must be occurring continuously. Thus, $W(x)$ which looks very static in terms of scattering is only an average. The particle is continuously scattering, with each $\sin(px)$ in $W(x)$ scattering into a set of other $\sin(kx)$'s and each of these in turn scattering into another set of $\sin(lx)$'s etc. A resonance with the potential needs to be established. Let us examine the time independent Schrodinger equation to see if it indicates how, such a resonance can occur.

$$-1/2m \sum_p p^2/2m f_p \sin(px) + V(x) W(x) = E W(x) \quad ((1))$$

The second term $V(x)W(x)$ can be thought of as a scattering term, it seems. One may write $V(x)$ as a Fourier series and also $W(x)$ as a Fourier series. The various $\exp(ikx)$ terms from $V(x)$ will combine with $\exp(ipx)$ to create $\exp(i(k+p)x)$ terms, which can then be written as $\sin((k+p)x)$ if there is a certain symmetry in the system. Thus, ((1)) can be written in terms of each $\sin(px)$, namely:

$$-1/2m p^2/2m f_p \sin(px) + \sum_{k+l=p} V(k)\exp(ikx) f_l \exp(ilx) = E f_p \sin(px)$$

In the second term, the $\exp(i(k+l)x)$ will combine with $\exp(-i(k+l)x)$ to form $\sin((k+l)x) = \sin(px)$. Thus, it is argued that the physics of the problem is described by the second term, which involves many different $\sin(lx)$ terms from $W(x)$ scattering with $V(x)$ to form $\sin(px)$. Thus, $\sin(px)$

in $p^2/2m \sin(px)$ and $E \sin(px)$ is really a representation of this scattering. The factor E on the right hand side of the equation shows that there is a cycling time of $1/E$ for this process.

Given that $\sin(px)$ is really a product of various $\sin(kx)$'s scattering with $V(x)$, the question seems to be whether the scattering of a zitterbewegung particle with $V(x)$ differs from that of a point particle, or in other words, can the zitterbewegung interaction with $V(x)$ account for interference? Consider a particle undergoing zitterbewegung modeled by $\sin(px)$ which seems to hold for a particle in a box with no potential. Then for different x , there is a different probability of the particle being present due to its internal motion. This should affect the interaction with $V(x)$ at a point x . At x , the force is $-dV(x)/dx$, but unlike the classical case, the particle is not at x , it is only at x with a probability. Thus, a particle with a center of mass at x , could actually be at position $x+\delta$ within a wavelength with a lower probability. Thus, writing $V(x)\sin(px)$ for the positive values of $\sin(px)$ may make sense.

Next, one has to explain the negative values of $\sin(px)$, which is more difficult. The question arises as to the meaning of such negative values. The particle in a box also has negative $\sin(px)$ values which have the same density as the positive ones. In the 2×2 matrix model (1), it was suggested that a particle moves back and forth in an internal cycle while moving forward with an average v . The positive and negative values of $\sin(px)$ might describe this forward and backward motion. For a non-interacting particle, the positive and negative signs simply indicate a different process is occurring. If a potential is present, however, the interaction of a quantum particle as it is in its forward zitterbewegung motion may be the negative of that of when it is in its backward motion. Thus, there are physical consequences of this forward and backward motion when interactions occur. It is suggested that this may explain why a $\sin(px)$ term from $W(x)$ can contribute a negative value in $V(x)W(x)$ at x while a $\sin(kx)$ might contribute a positive. The potential $V(x)$ is also contributing negative and positive $\sin(lx)$ values as it seems to also have the same kind of forward and backward motion when interacting with a zitterbewegung particle.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it seems difficult to describe the physical origins of interference in quantum mechanics. The wavefunction $W(x)$ written as a Fourier series contains various $\sin(px)$ terms which can add or subtract (interfere), but it is not clear why. Even more confusing is the fact that interference occurs in calculations of average kinetic energy or kinetic energy density which include $\sum_p p^2/2m \sin(px)$. For a particle in a box, which has a $\sin(px)$ wavefunction, the kinetic energy is $p^2/2m$ everywhere so it is not at all clear why interference should "switch" on because scattering occurs. If one considers, however, that a $\sin(px)$ term is created due to scattering described by $V(x)W(x)$, then it is possible that the $\sin(px)$ behaviour in $W(x)$ affects the way in which this particle with zitterbewegung interacts with the potential. If a particle is moving backward and forwards while moving with an average v in the forward direction, then positive and negative $\sin(px)$ values may describe the interaction during these two very different motions. In such a case, the interference is really a consequence of how a quantum particle interacts with a potential.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Is Quantum Mechanics Contained in Special Relativity? (preprint, zenodo, 2018)